

Finite element analysis of tow designs investigating the differences between a single piece and two pieces models

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Abstract

This study is analyzing the difference between 2 different implant systems. State of art in mechanical engineering analysis is the FEA (finite element analysis). In mechanical engineering, it is used before almost all other engineering applications. It could be applied as well to evaluate other situations such as that of the medical implants. It is not peculiar to the implant system, but rather to give a deep insight into what is the results of interaction of the biodevices with the biological systems. Modern orthopedics spot the light on different effects of the biomaterials on the biosystems. Significant clinical results variation between the two types of systems were analyzed and demonstrated. Two pieces of implant model is poor in function, both in the distribution of stresses due to results of the loading lead to a certain type of stress shielding and also to the corrosion between the components of this type of implant. Further development of the single piece implant with more awareness about the hidden shortcomings of the 2 pieces systems must be held in mind when picking out between different systems

Keywords: Finite element analysis, dental implant, 2 pieces implant, single piece implant, stress shielding, titanium corrosion

General introduction about implants

The dental implant is a good solution that can provide a partial or completely edentulous patient with a robust functional and aesthetic solution they are now the standard for oral rehabilitation in case of partial or complete edentulism (1)

It had great success rates when osseointegration is gained and sufficient oral hygiene is maintained (2)

An implant-supported denture is equal in functioning like the ordinary dentures (3)

The success rate of a dental bridge when supported by dental implants is favorable than that supported by the natural teeth, and also better to use dental implant instead of natural teeth (4)

An implant is even more mechanically robust and full arch can be extremely successful and held by just (4) implants (5)

Osseointegration is stiffer, stronger and non-specific in comparison to the attachment of the bone to the natural teeth.

Theoretically, if a crown of a natural tooth put over the implant, failure mostly ensued Even when the forces generated by the occlusion on implants is much higher than those generated by natural dentition

The most 2 causes for this huge force generation are the absence of the proprioception, nature of the osseointegration and using stiff rigid material when doing the prosthetic part of the implant

Dental implant systems had many variations between them, especially in the design. The implant will face many chemical and mechanical challenges during its functioning intraorally. Biocompatibility of the implant, affected by its design, may lead to a different pattern of bone remodeling around the implant, although how the stresses and strains start this response is still without a clear image in the scientist imagination (6)

Implant longevity is directly correlated with its mechanical properties, surface nature, and design. The selection basis of the biomedical designs should be built upon the best knowledge based on the scientific pieces of evidence rather than anything else.

When there is thin gingiva the tissue at the implant emergence will be modified to take the final contour of the underlying osseous structure.

Soft tissue width had a great effect upon the crestal bone resorption. The biological width ($\geq 3\text{mm}$) will be established finally (7) (8), even if this leads to bone resorption, as in the case of thin gingiva (9). Every effort must be made to keep bone on the safe side. And the factors that lead to bone resorption should be avoided

Introduction regarding 2 pieces

The vast majority of the implant design composed of two pieces connected by a screw

The connection between the implant and abutment plays a significant role in the net result of the biocompatibility of the implant as it could offer a direct impact upon the living tissues (10). When the implant-abutment connection is shifted more gingivally the bone resorption will be less. Some systems make the implant design different so that the 2 piece implant is placed $\geq 1.5\text{ mm}$ over the crest so that to ensue distant connection of the implant from the bone to minimize the negative effect on the bone from the implant-abutment connection (11)

The platform switching provides a good example of how the macro design of the medical devices could affect the biocompatibility of these devices

This modification of the implant design (platform switching), although was discovered by chance due to marketing issue, it brought great advances to the correction dilemma of the crestal bone resorption (12)

Platform switching reduces the crestal bone resorption to a great extent (13). Nevertheless, it is based upon the clinical results rather than a clear scientific explanation. The most accepted theories behind the effect of platform switching are:

- Thicker soft tissue
- Far micro motion from the bone
- Shifting of the abutment implant gap that may contain bacteria away from the bone

Many systems had more hermetic seal between the implant and the abutment than others, this due to many causes one of them is the bioengineering vision of the manufacturing company.

The site of microgap between the implant and abutment play a significant role on the peri-implant soft tissue, which can be regarded as a major player in the success of the dental implant treatment (10)

The distant connection from the bone and soft tissue with more robust application of the mechanical engineering concepts (such as tapered connection) promote healthier tissues' growth with more connective tissue principal components (abundant fibroblast and collagen fibers accompanied by less inflammatory response). While in the case of the non-platform

switching connection (ordinary locking system), more delicate tissue with more intense inflammatory response apparent through the presence of different inflammatory cells (10). Even the previous study suggest that the connection type is more important determinant and had a more beneficial effect than the platform switching (10)

Comparison between 2 and 1

Even when no movement of the abutment has happened, (8) as in case of 2 piece implant, the unloaded implant had shown a significant decrease of resorption of the crestal bone in case of a one-piece implant in comparison to 2 piece implant (8) 15

A recent study showed a significant difference between bacteriological environments around the one-piece implant in comparison to the 2 piece implants (14).

Many products in the market composed of single pieces implant and the companies try by this method to eliminate the gap between the 2 pieces implant parts

The effect of the 2 piece implant is not related just of the dynamic movement of the implant due to forces exerted upon the abutment, we attribute this to the possible bacterial colonization of the gap inherited in the 2 pieces implant system and the corrosion that is happening even in the static conditions (such as fretting and crevicular corrosion). The one-piece implant had a higher mechanical properties (14)

The great difference between the strength of the 2 piece implant and single-piece implant concerning mechanical failure can be easily demonstrated with the narrow diameter implant. This failure can give a strong insight into what may happen in the case of wide implants (14)

The transgingival area of the 1 piece implant is much stronger mechanically than that of the 2 piece implant (14). The one-piece implant had proven to have great reliability according to the high success rates (15). This has many causes such as ease of use and simplicity of the surgical procedure.

The one-piece implant now had a wide acceptance and its preferences over the 2 pieces implant are gaining more by the oral surgeons (15)

This retrospective study showed that about third of the one-piece implants (65 of 176) the level of the crestal bone had gained new positive height in the follow-up period after the surgery (15)

The presence of many varieties of the implant superstructure facilitates the vast majority of the prosthodontics rehabilitation challenges. The bone resorption pattern of the alveolar ridge after teeth extraction is different across individuals and many times resorption makes from the ridge not suitable to receive one-piece implant as the long axis of the implant will compromise the prosthetic replacement. The net result that the patient is waiting for from the implant placement and obligate using conventional methods to modify the implant (16).

It is right that the 2 pieces of implant provide better prosthetic treatment options, but this is on the cost of tissue healthiness. In case of the one-piece implant, the undisturbed growth and maturation of the soft tissue due to which not happened in the vast majority of 2 pieces

implant due to different components manipulation and procedures lead to more resorption of the crestal bone (12)

Even when single implant had many limitations and cannot be a rival the 2 piece implant, scalloped implant design is a great modification of the one-piece implant that combines the benefit of the one-piece implant with the non-compromised aesthetics of other systems (17) (18)

Introduction about FEA

FEA is an engineering method used to test the mechanical properties of the structures and designs. It was the first time used for the aircraft industry product (19)

It is a reliable method in dental material tests. When you had a complex design and want to test it, you had 2 methods

1. Manufacture it and test it a real lab environment, which has many limitations and it may be expensive as it may need a new model every time you want to conduct the test.
2. By doing FEA to select the best model that gives the insights on suggesting the best prototype model.

How could we represent the material inside of the FEA?

Simply take a cube of the material and do all the tests upon it, now make tiny cubicles (or let's say finite elements) and build your virtual model from them. The complex design derives its complex behavior from the properties of the tiny cubicle (finite elements), which is formed from.

Comings of the FEA (finite element analysis) are countless, no material loss as it is performed at virtual lab, any circumstances (temperature, humidity etc.) can be simulated,

no ethical or legal obligations etc. (19)

In most circumstances, validation of the FEA is a very important step, as the results must be confirmed before taking a decision and building the assembly, but in our study, the FEA gives a comprehensive explanation of the cause of certain mechanical problems and give an acceptable explanation of some aspect of the implant performance. The validation is already present even before the commencement of the FEA study, as many of the well-known rules coincide with our findings.

In many times, supposing the biological systems as engineering units is an enormous error. The simplest example is the dealing with the bone as a plastic material exactly like a (PMMA). They are not alike, but unfortunately in all known studies, we do suppose they are alike when conducting the FEA.

The bone had fascinating adaptive capacity, amazing complex composite structure both microscopically and macroscopically, extremely complicated sensory feedback system, no definitive shape across individuals and interindividually at different times, complex viscoelasticity etc.

The ability of bone structure reforming, after its cleavage gives the bone its unique feature of bone repair which is not seen in any mechanical system other than living tissues.

One study even reported compact bone instead of cancellous bone in the apical 2 thirds instead of cancellous bone in the area surround dental implant (20), which mean that even after load the mechanical features of the bone had been enhanced

A recent report of human retrieval case showed that the implant is surrounded by mature lamellar bone following the shape of the implant (21), which mean that the anisotropy of the bone is changing with the applied load

We do the modeling of bone as other FEA do, modeling two portions: outer as cortical and inner as cancellous

The type of the material used in the FEA that represent the bone must be restudied well as we think this method of modeling, especially of dental implants, is not the exact representation of the reality

This can be done by real registration of implant movement in vivo and model the bone by different configurations, and the one that gives closer to the in vivo model could be adopted. This work is beyond the scope of this research and needs highly sophisticated mechanical engineering inspection tools

A study showed even when there is damage to the osseointegration around the implant it was cohesive rather than adhesive, which means that the bone destruction from the bone rather than the interface between the bone and the implant. The failure of the implant is happening in the peri-implant trabecular bone component of the implant anchorage apparatus and it is more important for implant survival than the BIC, and suggest targeting of the trabecular thickness of the peri-implant trabecular bone 26

Overload: the innocent accused vs titanium corrosion: the real actor

The concept of overloading had never been established and it is a matter of controversy (22). Sometimes it is a speculative term (23)

Nevertheless, some define it to encompass the implant and bone (24), and the mechanical response of the implant material to the applied stresses can be calculated precisely, the response of the bone to stress and strain is not presentable as the mechanical model of the living bone is still not defined and clear

Due to many limitations of the study of the effect of implant overload in humans, the animal gives strong evidence of what is happening in this situation. We consider similar bone resorption pattern in humans to that in animals as they have the same pattern of wound healing and bone apposition when having an implant inserted intraosseously, and many animals show bone activity near to that of the humans (25). Whenever a material subjected to stress above its endurance limit, it will be weaker and the successive stresses will ultimately induce fatigue failure. But in case of the bone, unlike all materials, whenever you apply a stress within its physiological limit, you will find it stronger next time. Continuous application of these stress would make the endurance limit of the bone greater than its primary ultimate stress. Unfortunately, studies on the overload in implantology field is scarce (22)

What makes us suspect the rule of overload as damaging to the implant anchorage apparatus is these reasons:

- Periimplantitis is a major component of this condition and it must be found to guarantee the effect of overload to be active

- The pattern of bone loss due to overload is different from that of the bone damage by osteolysis such as that result from biofilm induced damage (22)

- Complete loss of osseointegration is peculiar to the old studies, while it is not replicated in the more recent studies, implicating the evident development of a better understanding of biomechanical concepts and usages of these concepts as standards in the biomedical industry (26)

Another thing must be clear when speaking about implantable devices, is titanium corrosion. Titanium contributes too many total hip arthroplasties` failures due to local tissue reaction 32 Titanium outer layer can be disturbed easily and it offers the titanium or titanium alloys their noble features mostly in the static condition.

Titanium alloys had low shear strength and susceptible to sever wear in comparison to other metal alloys. This is one of the limitations of Titanium usage in the bioengineering application (27).

Titanium particles due to the implant insertion friction with the bone bed had been reported as well as some threads of the implant had been deformed and fractures of the bone trabeculae adjacent to the deformed threads had been shown (28)

Titanium is a toxic element if got involved corrosion and when implant this element as a hard tissue replacement, it must keep away from corrosion and keep away from the sites that had friction between its parts.

Titanium alloys producing so more particles than Co-Cr-Mo when friction between metallic components occur (29)

Many claims to stop the usage of titanium alloys and quit its usages in orthopedic products such like joint articulating surfaces due to its health hazards, this is from the era of ninety (30), and we must reconsider the design of dental implants according to the latest findings in the orthopedic surgery.

Even when the histology of the titanium implants showed its high bioinertness due to the unique osseous tissue response to it in case of intraosseous placement (such as inherited high corrosion resistance, no toxicity upon cells and the distinctive non-inflammatory response ... etc.) (28), the direct effect of the titanium wear debris on the peri-implant tissues had been addressed frequently as one of the major failures in total joint arthroplasties (31)

Why we conduct our research

We conduct this study to investigate deeply the difference between the 2 pieces implant and single-piece implant. The internal stresses and strains cannot be easily estimated manually, but the FEA analysis is a powerful tool to fulfill this job

FEA packages had extensive capabilities of representing different materials and different designs behavior in any combination and arrangement or situation, all this is done in easily understood graphs

The graphs can be analyzed and a comparison between different models could be done. And the capability to do this comparison is not exclusive to the engineering staff which could be involved in only obtain these results.

Many claim that less stress in the bone is better, but as the most clinical and research data indirectly show the opposite, we try to explore what could be happening in vivo.

Conflicting findings need deep investigations to explain the missing parts of the picture to reconcile between these results.

The most likely cause of more bone loss in the 2 piece implant to the pattern of stresses distribution and the more corrosion that caused by the internal friction and dissimilarity of the 2 pieces implant as the major cause for crestal bone resorption

As most of the 2 pieces metallic implants (made from titanium or titanium alloys) are mainly composed of different materials, spontaneous types of corrosion (crevicular and galvanism corrosion), will be imperative.

Materials and methods

Solidworks premium 2017 and SOLIDWORKS® Simulation 2017 was used to get the FEA results. AVENTUM 3 PRO workstation was used to obtain the results

We conduct FEA to show the difference between the simple design of 2 piece implant (abutment and implant connected by a screw) and a single piece implant

Another design consisted of the same 2 pieces model, but the abutment was considered as a single unit with the implant but without connecting screw.

This hollow design is to see the effect of the hollow space on the implant

In the situation of the 2 pieces implant, the connecting screw was supposed to be perfectly united with the implant without any rotational movement, to limit the effects of the force only by that caused by the abutment.

The design was representing a screw-shaped implant with an internal hex. The gaps between the implant and abutment were neglected, a perfect setting was assumed.

In the reality, the results will be worse as we considered perfect idealization, and it is well-known in the mechanical engineering the manufacturing flaws would cause the failure such as the small scratch may be considered as stress concentration region and failure will begin from.

Material used as follow :

- The crown supposed to be made from monolithic dental zirconia as it had very high mechanical strength, highest modulus of elasticity among the other dental materials, excellent aesthetic and globally regards one of the benchmark materials used for crown and bridge manufacturing. Global daily production estimation is about 15000 – 20000 unit –supplemental 3
- Implant, abutment and the connecting screw were supposed from high strength titanium alloy (modulus of elasticity = 113 MPa, yield strength = 790 MPa and Poisson's ratio = 0.342
- The cortical and cancellous bone was supposed to be as fellow:
 - Cortical bone (modulus of elasticity 13.7 MPa, Poisson's ratio 0.3, yield strength 483)
 - Cancellous bone (modulus of elasticity 1.37 MPa, Poisson's ratio 0.394, yield strength 106.8)

The type of the conducted study was linear as any deformation beyond the elastic limit is useless as we think. Plastic deformation will indicate the severe form of deformation. We want to examine just the part of the dynamicity that happens in the vast majority of the real cases

All the quality of the meshes used in our study was high to get the most accurate results, nevertheless, the needed time for calculation would be less if the quality were less.

The mesh properties of the 2 pieces model were:

- Total nodes 266355
- Total elements 194373

The mesh properties of the hollowed model were:

- Total nodes 216487
- Total elements 157080

The mesh properties of the solid model were:

- Total nodes 274155
- Total elements 200494

The result

The judgment on the design in mechanical engineering, which is the nearest engineering discipline to implant dentistry, is not easy and needs thorough evaluation of many aspects.

To demonstrate the difference between the 2 types, we had considered these criteria:

- The maximum stress that the 3 implant types produced
- The distribution of the resulted stresses and the occurrence site of its maximum value
- Strain energy density was considered as a criterion to demonstrate the possibility of early fatigue failure in the implant material (32), also it acts as a stimulus for regulation and control of bone remodeling process (33)
- 3rd. principal strain and 1st principal strain were considered to reveal the areas of compression and tension through the area of the surrounding bone
- Displacement was used for evaluation of the net flexibility of the implant used whether it had greater rigidity and deform less with the same deflecting forces
- Thanks to the great versatility of the used FEA package, by the normal strain in the direction to show the exact strain around the axis of rotation
- The factor of safety was used to take a preliminary idea about design safety and where most areas will fail first

Discussion

Von mises stress results

The maximum von mises stresses generated by the 2 pieces implant was ten times greater than what had happened in one piece implant in our study.

The area of the maximum stresses was in the abutment implant interface in case of 2-piece implant and at the side opposite to the site of the force application.

Stresses in the bone in the area away from the direction of force receive less stress. This deprivation from stresses is one of the causes of more crestal bone resorption in case of 2-piece implant in comparison to one-piece implant

This had been pointed to implicitly, as the difference between the mesiodistal and buccolingual stresses distribution may induce less bone remodeling in the former in comparison to the latter (34)

Stress shielding is a recognized long term damaging phenomenon that accused to cause many failures of total arthroplasties

Some studies when doing the FEA just calculate the maximum stresses and deformation without considering the extent of these stresses or strains inside the whole supposed assembly. Other studies try different materials` combinations and designs` varieties to reduce the stress transferred to the bone (35)+ (36) + (37). They are dealing with the bone as a continuous isotropic engineering material.

This phenomenon is charged with causing refracture after long term rigid fixation. Increasing the flexibility of the bone plate is required to put the bone in more stressful status (38)

In contrast to what one might imagine according to the common belief, we consider the increase in the stress generated by the implant will have a more beneficial effect on the bone When viewing just the stresses above 20 MPa in the bone, it is important to note the limited stress distribution in the case of 2 pieces implant

Model name: 1 piece vs 2 piece solidworks work
Study name: 150 horizon two piece (Default)
Plot type: Static nodal stress Stress1
Deformation scale: 50
Volume (Element/Geometric) = 17.52 %/ 9.82 %

The bone must receive stress from the adjacent intrasosseous implanted device, otherwise, osteolysis will jeopardize the device as the surrounding bone could be put in severely weakened status, and any sudden shocking stress may result in damage to the bone (33) In contrast to what happens in the bone, more areas of implant engaged with a greater amount of stresses to the same implant type (2 pieces model).

The deformity that happens within the 2-piece implant absorbs most of the energy and transmits less stresses to the bone than that occur with a single-piece implant.

Increased fixation flexibility is advisable to reduce the risk of poor healing and to simulate proper physiological stresses delivered to the bone to fight the stress shielding (39)

The fracture may happen at the implant-abutment connection as it the weakest area in the 2-piece implant, and failure of the 2 pieces implant is difficult to treat as it involves multiple parts with precise dimensions and any miss fit between them lead to ensued failure and necessitate the retrieval of the implant.

When compare the failure mode of the 2-piece implant, fracture of the abutment screw and plastic deformity of the implant platform which rendering the implant useless in case of surgeon want to repair it (40)

In many studies, they showed that the cyclic fatigue may lead to implant mechanical failure in shorter times if exposed to the half of their ultimate stresses with every cycle (41)

The weakest point of the single piece implant is at the threads area. This was evident where the stresses concentrate in this area and the maximum stresses area is happening.

While the bending was happening more apically in the threaded zone of the one-piece implant, event after passing the first third of the threaded zone.

Continuous load on the implant by mean of orthodontic expansion screws attached to the abutment of the implant induce more bone apposition and promotion of greater BIC than the normally loaded implants. (42)

This is in contrast to other plastic materials where creep in some situations would cause material flow, deformity, and even failure might result

The effect of the experimental mucositis or ligature induced peri-implantitis had shown great detrimental effect upon the unloaded in contrary to the implant under continuous load (43), which is a great difference between bone and other non-vital material.

The model of bone creep so must be designated according to the remodeling activity which is the sole player in vital bone unique features. It is worthy to notice that even the static load had a variable time-dependent effect, in the begin it will cause positive effects but finally it may lead to bone loss. (44). BIC and bone densities dramatically benefit by overloading, even a study reported 3-5 mm higher occlusal surfaces of the implant than the adjacent dentition (22)

In contrast to the constantly applied load, dynamic load induces severe bone loss, in case of intentionally happened mucositis and ligature-induced peri-implantitis. When overloaded implant inducing the bone loss aided by ligature induced peri-implantitis as an essential aggravating factor, the bone loss in just confined around the neck of the implant (43)

From the former paragraphs and our findings, we suggest that the stresses are not harmful to the bone or at least not the sole player in the determination of the crestal bone stability.

Strain energy density

Strain energy density inside the implant structure was 7 folds greater in the two pieces implant in comparison to the one-piece implant. This leads to an accelerated deterioration of the implant and even more fatigue failures.

Even with less mass in case of a hollowed implant, the strain energy density was nearly the same as the solid implant

One of the well-accepted theory of bone remodeling numerical prediction is the adaptive remodeling theory which regards the strain energy density as the prime feedback factor in bone remodeling (45).

More profound strain energy density around the neck of a one-piece implant simply means the bone share to some degree of the deformation and help in return of implant to the original position after deflection happens when forces applied on it, and as we mentioned: mean more stress on the bone.

Our FEA about the strain energy density findings also consistent with other studies which support the same concept, the more strain energy density leads to more positive bone remodeling (46)

It's well-known clinically that some type of rehabilitation implant cause certain pattern of selective bone resorption and apposition, this results shown the same when FEA had been done to simulate the strain energy density, and the next suggestion of the FEA is that when changing the design of the implant will change the strain energy density that gives better physiological stress distribution (46)

When the diameter of the implant is small this will lead to an even smaller diameter of the abutment, as the implant must retain sufficient walls thickness to tolerate the mechanical stresses.

Implementation of platform switching in almost all implant systems nowadays, making the neck of the abutment where it is connecting to the implant is smaller.

Due to the weakness inherited in the small-diameter implant of the 2 pieces implant, it must be used with caution, and most manufacturers restrict this product to the lower incisors only (47)

The strength of the one-piece implant is double of that of the 2 pieces implant with the same diameter is about double (48), and many recommend not to use them in all situations

Strains

1st principal strain

3rd principal strain

Location of the maximum value of the 1st principal strain at the site of force direction in case of 2 pieces implant can be explained as follows:

When there is a complex geometry exerting force upon the adjacent structure in a given assembly the resultant maximum value may be aberrant as the meshing of the geometry

may give some sort of the triangulation that causes the resultant maximum value may not relate to the whole picture. This is recognized by the FEA experts.

When there are multiple meshes interaction in the FEA with separated entities or objects the bias in the highest value may be explained as we said due to deviation of one or more triangles of the surface of the solid mesh, and sometimes FEA engineering consider just the values with high contact area (46)

The induced strain in the bone due implant function limited to 1000-1500 micro-strain usually strengthen the bone, while 3000 micro-strain my do the opposite (49)

As the complex forces and reactionary forces may take the greatest value in a location other than most of the less value appears. It is right that it had the highest value, but the collection of the others in another place.

The distribution of the areas with more tension in the bone was as we expected in opposite direction to the force with greater involvement of cortical bone in tension areas in the case of a single piece implant than in the case of the two-piece implant.

Three areas of high compression was evident in the case of 2 piece implant, at the connection and between the abutment and implant.

These areas where we expect most of the fretting corrosion will occur. As sliding occurs in all of these areas, as we will show in the next, the corrosion will be more intense

Third part wear claimed to cause more damage to the implant surfaces when titanium is used in frictional surfaces (30)

Displacement results

The displacement of all examples (single piece, hollowed and 2 piece implant), was having the same pattern within the crown.

Limited range of displacement indicated by the narrowing of the medium color bands in the case of 2 piece implants was a clear example of the more acute angle of bending of the 2 piece implant.

The maximum displacement of the 2 piece implant was 2 times greater than that of the single-piece implant. This finding is consistent with real lab experiment results (48).

The displacement of the 2 piece implant is significantly more in the abutment & crown region, and this lead to continuous stretching of the mucosa, and we consider this is one of the notorious effects from the 2 pieces implant, is not present the soft tissue around the one- piece implant that showed great resemblance to that of the natural teeth in case of 1 piece implant (11)

The addition of the hollowed portion to the implant had no significant effect upon the one- piece implant displacement. Displacement of the bone surrounding the different types of the implant was also different, the same pattern of stresses was evident and similar

Normal strain in the x direction results

Normal strain in the x direction demonstrate the clear representation of the extent of rotation due to the application of forces

Significant diminished of the tension in the opposite side of the forces in the bone is another demonstration of this pattern of the stress shields

Displacement other views

When the force is exerted upon the implant, the implant will rotate

Limitation of the displacement values range in the FEA range between $8e-3$ and $1e-5$ show the deformation of the body of the 2 prices implant in comparison to the hollowed implant or single piece implant

Relative displacement results

To demonstrate the relative displacement and sliding of the abutment inside the implant, probing of certain regions where we suspect the significant relative displacements are occurring at, was done. Surprisingly the relative movement of some points of the abutment may reach 32micron.

We consider these values significant, especially in the zero-tolerance model. Sometimes due to conflicts of interests, many claim the best design, but no voice could drown out the voice of numbers.

When exaggerating the deformity of the 2-piece implant up to 50 times the new oval shape of the implant neck cross-section is apparent. It indicates that the new shape of the circular cross-section of the implant is converted into an ellipsoidal shape.

Displacement of the implant neck area opposite to the force direction reached about 18micron but on the site with the force direction will reach 24 microns, and the difference could be a gap for passage of bacteria.

The presence of bacteria and toxins or other noxious materials in the deep area at the connection between the implant and abutment is proven and could produce a continuous state of injury to the peri-implant tissue that could lead to peri-implantitis and implant failure.

The different sizes of the micro gap between the abutment and the implant across different implant systems had shown no significant effect upon the crestal bone resorption in contrast to the remoteness of this gap from the bone (11) (50)

The effect of the implant-abutment connection type on the crestal bone is controversial (50), and we do emphasize that the 2 piece implant will ultimately have the nearly same result even with different extent

Experimental inclusion of titanium particles showed a significant weakening of the osteoblastic activity coincided with high RANKL pathway activation, the main signal of the osteoclasts differentiation

The osteoblasts attenuation is constantly evident with different particles` sizes, although each size had a different pathway for osteoblasts attenuation. Titanium as bulk material had excellent bioinertness 51, but its particles behave differently (51)

It must be emphasized upon the fact that common size of the titanium particles which had been found in the retrieval studies in orthopedics ranges are (1-10 micron) may in many circumstances not be shown locally as its systemic clearance may obscure this (51)

Another study to simulate the initiation of aseptic total joint replacements failure or loosening had shown also significant less osteoblastic activity and the rule of titanium particles on the macrophages that results in a similar pattern of the membrane engulfing the failed joint replacement (52)

The effect of Titanium particles phagocytosis on macrophages results in releasing cytokines that inducing bone loss & osteolysis and acute response to titanium particles, which lead to bone loss that is not reversible (53), and this cannot cause by the implant inter-parts friction only, but also from external sources such as ultrasonic scaling.

The small but dynamic movement of the abutment inside of the implant and due to weak wear resistance of the titanium alloy lead to Titanium particles release from the implant The phenomenon of Titanium particles release from the friction of multi-component implantable devices is not confined to the dental implants, as this had been recorded in the Titanium plates used for fractures fixations. Titanium particles in soft tissue will result in

granulomatous reaction and discoloration in tissues surrounding titanium implants due to the release of particles that were evident in half of the retrieved implants in one study (54). In the same previous study, the wear happened at the plate screw junction.

Fluids flow & turbidity inside of Titanium or Titanium alloys tubes are well-known in the engineering applications

It is well-known that the fluid flow will cause the titanium particles to be detached, although this is not significant in the humans as the flow event in the major vessels is below the threshold limit of this phenomenon, but this must be kept in mind as a guide to demonstrate some weakness associated within the material or its alloy usage in biomedical application. The oxide needle model theory for characterization of titanium oxide passive layer that surrounds the titanium explain titanium particle release from the surface where no observable friction or tribology had occurred, especially in our case as in the soft tissue discoloration (54)

Unfortunately, osteoclasts that are differentiated due to action of titanium particles is affected only to a small extent by these particles and their action will not be jeopardized (55).

The corrosion of the titanium implants is happening and continuously uninterrupted, changing the implant shape and size. One interesting observation is that even the peri-implant bed of the sandblasted titanium femoral stem had been polished, and this is caused by rubbing with the bed which is non-metallic (56)

Even with materials having one of the lowest value of the friction coefficient such as polyethylene, titanium release significantly more wear debris in comparison to other metals alloys, and titanium had extreme friction coefficient with a consistent feature of premature wear in prosthesis made from (57)

Due to the higher solubility of the Titanium, it may not affect the local tissues only and may not be feasible to show this element locally as it will be cleared

This evident through the raising of blood titanium ions significantly in patients receives artificial joint replacement and may disseminate to distant organs and systems (58)

A systematic review concluded that the abutment material is one of the factors that determine the stability of the peri-implant bone level (58). This may be because the wear rate between ceramic and metal is lesser than between metals and the interruption of many types of corrosion such as crevicular and galvanism

Wear products from metal on metal total hip arthroplasty, which is high load-bearing joint, is much more than from ceramic on metals bearing surfaces. Approximately the latter is about 1% of the former (59)

The ceramic on metal combination is encouraged even in the young active patient where service life expectancy is very high and high mechanical load and shocks will face the joint (60)

It must be noticed that even the coating of titanium surfaces with ceramic such as titanium nitrate had proven to be poor maneuver as delamination is reported (61)

The range of the mechanical movement is not small at all which may be one of the causes of peri-implant bone loss (62), and careful reevaluation of the implant systems of two component must be done in the light of modern engineering investigations

Finally, when the micro-gap in case of the 2 pieces implant is shifted away from the bone, we just expose the soft tissues to the wear products rather than the bone with the less negative effect on the bone

Factor of safety

These paragraphs, in which area with the factor of safety less than 4.5 had been clipped, show clearly more area in danger in case of 2 piece implant in comparison to 1 piece implant

Conclusion

According to the revealed performance of the one-piece implant and 2-piece implant, it is apparent that one-piece implant outperforms the 2 pieces implant and more work should be done to enhance the design of the one-piece implant to lessen the limitation adhere to this type of implants

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